

LEARNING DELIVERY AND INSTRUCTIONAL AND SUPERVISORY PRACTICES OF PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOL HEADS IN THE SCHOOLS DIVISION OF MARINDUQUE: BASIS FOR MATHEMATICS CURRICULUM ENHANCEMENT PLAN

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the efficacy of instructional and supervisory practices implemented by public elementary school heads in delivering mathematics education during the SY 2019-2020, 2020-2021 and 2021-2022 within the Schools Division of Marinduque, Philippines. The population consists of all elementary school heads, including principals, head teachers, and teachers-in-charge, totaling 186 individuals, along with 90 Master Teachers. Through total enumeration, the entire population was included in the sample, encompassing 186 elementary schools, 372 key teachers of Mathematics, master teachers, and nine Public Schools District Supervisors from Marinduque's SDO. A structured questionnaire served as the instrument for data collection, covering instructional improvement programs, management of instruction, instructional climate promotion, support to teaching and learning outcomes, and supervisory practices. Data were collected through electronic or printed questionnaires distributed to the identified respondents, with descriptive statistics like frequencies and percentages, as well as inferential statistics such as correlation and regression analysis, employed for data analysis using software like SPSS. The findings reveal a decrease in the intensity of instructional improvement programs during the pandemic, indicating challenges in adapting to remote and blended learning formats. Despite efforts to maintain an effective instructional climate, there was a decline in the frequency and effectiveness of instructional practices supporting teaching and learning outcomes in mathematics during the pandemic. Similarly, supervisory practices decreased, potentially impacting curriculum delivery and instruction quality. These findings stress the importance of ongoing efforts to enhance instructional practices and provide necessary support and resources to ensure effective teaching and learning outcomes in mathematics education, thereby improving the overall learning experience of students in Marinduque.

Keywords: *Learning Delivery, Instructional and Supervisory practices, School Heads, Mathematics curriculum*

INTRODUCTION

Education is a fundamental human right and plays a vital role in developing individuals and societies (UN, 2021). Education is a global concern, with the United Nations playing a pivotal role in advocating for equitable access to quality education worldwide. In recent years, there has been a growing recognition of education as a fundamental human right essential for individual empowerment and societal development. International frameworks, such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), emphasize the importance of education in achieving broader global objectives, including poverty reduction, gender equality, and economic growth. Moreover, the globalization of economies and rapid advancements in technology have reshaped educational paradigms, necessitating innovative approaches to teaching and learning to prepare students for the demands of the 21st century. (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization [UNESCO], 2019).

In the Philippines, education has long been recognized as a cornerstone of national development. The government has made significant strides in expanding access to education at all levels, with a particular focus on achieving universal primary education. Initiatives such as the K to 12 program have aimed to enhance the quality and relevance of education by aligning curriculum standards with global benchmarks. However, challenges persist, including disparities in educational access and quality between urban and rural areas, inadequate infrastructure and resources, and gaps in teacher training and professional development. Despite these challenges, there is a strong commitment at the national level to address these issues and ensure that every Filipino child receives a quality education. (Republic of the Philippines, 2013). The Philippines, as a signatory to the UN's Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), considers education a top priority and has implemented various policies and initiatives to provide quality education to all learners (Philippine Commission on Higher Education, 2020). Despite these efforts, challenges such as inadequate resources, lack of training, and insufficient support from school leaders persist, making it challenging to enhance the quality of learning delivery (Philippine Institute for Development Studies, 2020).

The COVID-19 pandemic has necessitated significant changes in the education sector, leading to new policies to ensure uninterrupted learning (Jain & Sharma, 2021). Distance learning has emerged as the most crucial and relevant learning method during the pandemic. However, its implementation requires extensive preparation of facilities to support instructors, institutions, and students. In response, the Department of Education in the Philippines has taken the initiative to implement alternative delivery modalities, which include the Modular Delivery Learning approach. This approach utilizes self-learning materials, online platforms, phone calls, and home visitations based on schedule for two-way under the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan.

Implementing modular distance learning modality during the first year has resulted in significant changes in the lives of both learners and teachers. The transition from a traditional classroom to a home learning environment has raised concerns, particularly for younger learners in elementary grades who may struggle with reading and numeracy (Galarion, 2021).

Mastering mathematics, in particular, has become a challenge for many learners as it requires a deep understanding of computation steps. In the province of Marinduque, poor performance in numeracy has been observed, with many students lacking the necessary skills to comprehend higher-level mathematics lessons and activities due to a lack of mastery in the four fundamental operations of addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division (Galarion, 2021).

To enhance learners' performance in subjects they have not yet mastered, effective instructional and supervisory practices are necessary. In this regard, school heads are crucial in supporting instruction and learning delivery. According to a study by Ilagan and Bautista (2018), the effectiveness of instructional and supervisory practices of school leaders is a critical factor that influences the quality of learning delivery, especially in mathematics. Elementary school heads, in particular, play a vital role in creating a conducive learning environment that enables learners to achieve their academic potential. They are responsible for ensuring that their schools are adequately equipped, teachers are competent and motivated, and learners receive quality education. Therefore, understanding their instructional and supervisory practices and how they influence the quality of learning delivery is crucial.

Instructional supervision is a process that assists teachers in enhancing the quality of the teaching and learning process and environment, with the primary objective of improving students' learning outcomes (Mohammed, 2015). Effective instructional supervision ensures that teachers use appropriate instructional strategies and materials, incorporate innovative technologies, and manage classroom behavior to achieve positive learning outcomes for students (Nwankwo & Owoyemi, 2017).

Changes in curriculum implementation can pose challenges for school heads in promoting an adequate instructional climate, supporting teaching, and learning outcomes, and managing school plants, resources, and facilities. However, with effective instructional supervision practices, school heads can mitigate these challenges and ensure students achieve positive learning outcomes. In summary, effective instructional and supervisory practices, under the leadership of school heads, are necessary to improve learners' performance in subjects they have not yet mastered. Instructional supervision is crucial in supporting teachers to improve the quality of teaching and learning processes, ultimately leading to improved student learning outcomes.

Supervision plays a crucial role in maintaining compliance with required policies and enhancing teacher effectiveness in schools. According to the literature, "supervision refers to overseeing, monitoring, and improving the quality of instruction in schools"

(Glickman, Gordon, & Ross-Gordon, 2014, p. 11). This oversight is necessary to ensure that teachers adhere to mandated policies and regulations and that they possess the required competence to provide effective instruction to their students.

Supportive communication strategies are equally important in sustaining teachers' dedication, competence, and performance. Research suggests that positive, constructive feedback from supervisors helps teachers feel valued and motivated, leading to increased engagement and better student outcomes (Hattie, 2012). Marinduque, a province in the Philippines, faces unique challenges in providing quality education to its residents. Situated in the Mimaropa region, Marinduque is characterized by its rural landscape and limited access to resources and services. Educational attainment levels in the province may be influenced by factors such as socio-economic status, geographical remoteness, and cultural traditions. Moreover, the COVID-19 pandemic has exacerbated existing educational inequalities, highlighting the need for targeted interventions to support teaching and learning in Marinduque. Understanding the local context is crucial for designing effective strategies to improve educational outcomes and address the specific needs of students and schools in the province (National Economic and Development Authority, 2018).

According to Galamay and Galarosa (2021), Marinduque, a province in the Philippines, is home to several public elementary schools that serve the educational needs of learners in the region. However, there is limited research on the instructional and supervisory practices of public elementary school heads in Marinduque and how these practices impact the quality of learning delivery, specifically in mathematics. Therefore, this study seeks to investigate the learning delivery and instructional and supervisory practices of public elementary school heads in the Schools Division of Marinduque; as a basis for enhancing the learning delivery of mathematics.

Specifically, the study evaluates the instructional and supervisory practices of public elementary school heads and proposes a curriculum enhancement program based on the findings. The goal of the curriculum enhancement program is to provide teachers with the necessary support, resources, and training to improve their instructional practices and enhance student learning outcomes. Overall, this study highlights the importance of adequate supervision and supportive communication strategies in improving teacher competence and student outcomes. By providing teachers with the necessary support and resources, schools can create a positive learning environment that fosters the development of both teachers and students.

Research Questions

The research aims to identify the current practices, challenges, and potential areas for improvement to enhance the delivery of Mathematics education in the province.

The main problem of this study is to evaluate the instructional and supervisory practices employed by public elementary school heads in the Schools Division of Marinduque, specifically in the context of Mathematics education.

Specifically, it aims to investigate the following:

1. What is the learning delivery of public elementary schools in Mathematics as measured by General Scholastic Average in the School Years 2019-2020, 2020-2021, and 2021-2022?
 2. What instructional practices are used by public elementary school heads in the learning delivery of Mathematics, as assessed by public school district supervisors, school heads, and master teachers, in terms of
 - 2.1 implementation of programs for instructional improvement,
 - 2.2 management of instruction,
 - 2.3 promotions of an effective instructional climate, and
 - 2.4 support for teaching and learning outcomes?
 3. What supervisory practices are used by public elementary school heads in the learning delivery of Mathematics, as assessed by public school district supervisors, school heads, and master teachers, in terms of
 - 3.1 supervision of the curriculum
 - 3.2 organization and personnel management
 - 3.3 planning, assessing, and reporting teaching and learning outcomes,
 - 3.4 management of school plant, resources, and facilities,
 - 3.5 development of personal, social, and professional growth of teachers; and
 - 3.6 development of school, community linkages, and public relations?
 4. How effective are the instructional and supervisory practices of public elementary school heads in the learning delivery of Mathematics, as assessed by public school district supervisors, school heads, and master teachers?
 5. How do instructional and supervisory practices of public elementary school heads affect the learning delivery of Mathematics, as assessed by public school district supervisors, school heads, and master teachers?
 6. What curriculum enhancements plan may be proposed by the researcher to improve the learning delivery in the area of Mathematics based on the study results?
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METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in the Schools Division of Marinduque, without mentioning specific institutions to maintain confidentiality. Total enumeration was used as the sampling method, involving all 186 elementary schools, 372 teachers, and nine District Supervisors. Respondents included school heads, teachers, and supervisors from various demographics within Marinduque.

Data was gathered through Google Forms, ensuring convenience and compliance with health protocols during the pandemic. The questionnaire used had three parts: GSA data collection, assessment of instructional practices, and evaluation of supervisory practices. It was designed with multiple items, utilizing Likert scales for responses. The questionnaire underwent pilot testing and validation to ensure reliability.

Quantitative analysis was conducted using descriptive statistics to summarize and analyze instructional and supervisory practices data. Mean scores and verbal interpretations were used to assess practice levels over three school years. The study's

scope was limited to Marinduque's educational division, and findings may not generalize to other regions. External factors beyond the study's scope could also influence mathematics performance.

RESULTS

Part I. Learning Delivery of Public Elementary Schools in Mathematics as measured by General Scholastic Average (GSA)

Table 2

Learning Delivery of Public Elementary Schools in Mathematics during the SY 2019-2020, 2020-2021 and 2021-2022, as Measured by General Scholastic Average

Grade Level	SY 2019-2020	Verbal Description	SY 2020-2021	Verbal Description	SY 2021-2022	Verbal Description
1	83.05	Satisfactory	80.88	Satisfactory	81.92	Satisfactory
2	76.57	Fairly Satisfactory	78.00	Fairly Satisfactory	78.14	Fairly Satisfactory
3	76.22	Satisfactory	80.00	Satisfactory	80.02	Satisfactory
4	75.92	Fairly Satisfactory	80.50	Satisfactory	80.97	Satisfactory
5	78.94	Fairly Satisfactory	79.49	Fairly Satisfactory	80.01	Satisfactory
6	79.48	Fairly Satisfactory	82.97	Satisfactory	80.13	Satisfactory
Total	78.36%	Fairly Satisfactory	80.31%	Satisfactory	80.20%	Satisfactory

*Legend: 90-100: Outstanding
85-89: Very Satisfactory
80-84: Satisfactory*

*75-79: Fairly Satisfactory
Below 75: Did Not Meet Expectations*

Table 3

Instructional Practices Used by Public Elementary School Heads in the Learning Delivery of Mathematics in terms of Implementation of Programs for Instructional Improvement,

Instructional Practices	SY 2019-2020		SY 2020-2021 - SY 2021-2022	
	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Coordination with the District/Division Offices in the implementation of DepEd programs and projects at the school level in the area of Mathematics (like MTAP Saturday Class, MTAP Competition, Early Language and Numeracy (ELLN), and the like).	4.50	Always Practiced	3.21	Sometimes Practiced
2. Orientation of teachers on updates in the teaching of content-area of Mathematics (e.g., updates on teaching K to 12 Curriculum Guide in Mathematics, Most Essential Learning Competencies in Mathematics, Curriculum of Mathematics of Special Science Class and the like)	4.52	Always Practiced	3.89	Frequently Practiced
3. Provision of explicit instructional support in the area of Mathematics like INSET (focusing on Least Mastered Competencies for Improvement), SLAC, and the like.	4.51	Always Practiced	3.76	Frequently Practiced
4. Advocacy of math and thinking skills for young children through community connect and remote instruction.	4.22	Always Practiced	3.77	Frequently Practiced
5. Implementation and close monitoring of school-based programs that promote numeracy (e.g., Project 1 PAD -One Problem A Day, School Math Camp, and the like).	4.28	Always Practiced	3.28	Sometimes Practiced
<i>Legend: 4.21 - 5.00: Always Practiced</i>		<i>1.81 - 2.60: Occasionally Practiced</i>		
<i>3.41 - 4.20: Frequently Practiced</i>		<i>1.00 - 1.80: Never Practiced</i>		
<i>2.61 - 3.40: Sometimes Practiced</i>				

Table 3.1

Instructional Practices Used by Public Elementary School Heads in the Learning Delivery of Mathematics in terms of Management of Instruction

Instructional Practices	SY 2019-2020		SY 2020-2021-SY 2021-2022	
	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Provision of technical assistance to teachers to promote collaborative work on math problems, relating math problems to real-world experiences, introducing math games and puzzles, and working on timed activities.	4.52	Always Practiced	3.72	Frequently Practiced
2. Provision of explicit instruction to support practice in the use of effective teaching strategies in the content area of mathematics	4.52	Always Practiced	3.73	Frequently Practiced
3. Provision of support management to teachers like how to handle the activities in the classroom and even in virtual platforms to make those effective and interesting.	4.40	Always Practiced	3.90	Frequently Practiced
4. Suggestions to teachers for classroom management in teaching mathematics in particular those who are handling double-grade or multi-grade	4.29	Always Practiced	3.74	Frequently Practiced
5. Assistance to teachers in providing information about each child's achievement and suggestion of specific activities to help the pupils when he or she does not learn what is presented in a lesson in Mathematics	4.47	Always Practiced	3.99	Frequently Practiced
<i>Legend: 4.21 - 5.00: Always Practiced</i>		<i>1.81 - 2.60: Occasionally Practiced</i>		
<i>3.41 - 4.20: Frequently Practiced</i>		<i>1.00 - 1.80: Never Practiced</i>		
<i>2.61 - 3.40: Sometimes Practiced</i>				

Table 3.2

Instructional Practices Used by Public Elementary School Heads in the Learning Delivery of Mathematics in terms of Promotion of an Effective Instructional Climate

Instructional Practices	SY 2019-2020		SY 2020-2021-SY 2021-2022	
	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Implementation of remote learning due to the pandemic situation in designated areas in the community	3.83	Frequently Practiced	4.22	Always Practiced
2. Management of classroom and school premises by following Safety protocols	4.12	Frequently Practiced	4.53	Always Practiced
3. Fostering of safe and healthy learning environment.	4.62	Always Practiced	4.64	Always Practiced
4. Collaboration with the community to maintain a child-friendly school and premises.	4.72	Always Practiced	4.50	Always Practiced
5. Creation of Math Park ideas in the school premises (Math Park Murals, Math Park Playground)	3.71	Frequently Practiced	3.00	Sometimes Practiced
<i>Legend: 4.21 - 5.00: Always Practiced</i>		<i>1.81 - 2.60: Occasionally Practiced</i>		
<i>3.41 - 4.20: Frequently Practiced</i>		<i>1.00 - 1.80: Never Practiced</i>		
<i>2.61 - 3.40: Sometimes Practiced</i>				

Table 3.3

Instructional Practices Used by Public Elementary School Heads in The Learning Delivery of Mathematics in Terms of Support to Teaching and Learning Outcome

Instructional Practices	SY 2019-2020		SY 2020-2021-SY 2021-2022	
	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Support the use of instructional technology in improving performance in Mathematics.	4.51	Always Practiced	4.13	Frequently Practiced
2. Identification of relevant curriculum and instruction when observing lessons in the content areas in mathematics.	4.51	Always Practiced	4.06	Frequently Practiced
3. Provision of essential content knowledge to support numeracy and mastery of content areas in mathematics through training of teachers in critical concepts.	4.43	Always Practiced	3.95	Frequently Practiced

4. Assistance and mentoring of teachers to deliver accurate and updated content knowledge using appropriate methodologies, approaches, and strategies in teaching Mathematics.	4.60	Always Practiced	4.10	Frequently Practiced
5. Conference with teachers to improve least mastered skills in Mathematics	4.66	Always Practiced	4.26	Always Practiced
<i>Legend: 4.21 - 5.00: Always Practiced</i>		<i>1.81 - 2.60: Occasionally Practiced</i>		
<i>3.41 - 4.20: Frequently Practiced</i>		<i>1.00 - 1.80: Never Practiced</i>		
<i>2.61 - 3.40: Sometimes Practiced</i>				

Table 4

Supervisory Practices Used by Public Elementary School Heads in the Learning Delivery of Mathematics in terms of Supervision of Curriculum

Supervisory Practices	SY 2019-2020		SY 2020-2021-SY 2021-2022	
	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Determination of the degree of curriculum alignment in the content area of Mathematics through classroom and teachers' observation.	4.53	Always Practiced	3.95	Frequently Practiced
2. Improvement of classroom teaching and learning through the provision of assistance to teachers and feedback to improve the focus of teaching on the least mastered skills in Mathematics for a continuous improvement of learners' performance	4.60	Always Practiced	3.97	Frequently Practiced
3. Supervision locally available instructional materials/resources that would be beneficial to the teacher in curriculum delivery and improve instruction through effective instruction of Mathematics	4.54	Always Practiced	3.97	Frequently Practiced
4. Maintaining standards or benchmarks, meeting delivery targets within time frames, as well as checking resistance in teachers and learners in Mathematics.	4.36	Always Practiced	3.80	Frequently Practiced
5. Maintenance and tracking of learner's value-added progress (VAP) records in Mathematics	4.42	Always Practiced	3.93	Frequently Practiced

Legend: 4.21 - 5.00: Always Practiced 1.81 - 2.60: Occasionally Practiced
 3.41 - 4.20: Frequently Practiced 1.00 - 1.80: Never Practiced
 2.61 - 3.40: Sometimes Practiced

Table 4.1
Supervisory Practices Used by Public Elementary School Heads in the Learning Delivery of Mathematics in terms of Organization and Personnel Management

Supervisory Practices	SY 2019-2020		SY 2020-2021-SY 2021-2022	
	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Ensuring effective time management through monitoring of teacher presence and attendance to duty	4.25	Always Practiced	4.56	Always Practiced
2. Ensuring adherence of teachers to school-related timetables and activities like staff meetings (focusing on the least mastered skills in Math and appropriate intervention) co-curriculum activities (MTAP Classes and Competition) and In-Service Training related to improving teaching and learning of Mathematics	4.56	Always Practiced	3.87	Frequently Practiced
3. Delegation of important responsibilities such as chairing subject coordination (e.g., Math Coordinator, MTAP Coordinator, a key teacher in Math) among others	4.57	Always Practiced	3.98	Frequently Practiced
4. Provision of feedback to staff to improve coordination and instruction	4.59	Always Practiced	4.25	Always Practiced
5. Coordination among teachers in the process of improving teaching and learning activities in Mathematics and in schools as a whole (like staff meetings)	4.63	Always Practiced	4.22	Always Practiced

Legend: 4.21 - 5.00: Always Practiced 1.81 - 2.60: Occasionally Practiced
 3.41 - 4.20: Frequently Practiced 1.00 - 1.80: Never Practiced
 2.61 - 3.40: Sometimes Practiced

Table 4.2

Supervisory Practices Used by Public Elementary School Heads in the Learning Delivery of Mathematics in Terms of Planning, Assessing, and Reporting Teaching Learning Outcomes

Supervisory Practices	SY 2019-2020		SY 2020-2021-SY 2021-2022	
	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Development and utilization variety of appropriate assessment strategies to monitor and evaluate teaching and learning in Mathematics	4.52	Always Practiced	4.01	Frequently Practiced
2. Provision of timely and accurate feedback to teachers to encourage them to reflect on and monitor their own teaching/professional growth	4.56	Always Practiced	4.18	Frequently Practiced
3. Evaluation of records of grades and performance of teachers and learners.	4.70	Always Practiced	4.39	Always Practiced
4. Development and utilization of creative and appropriate instructional planning.	4.57	Always Practiced	4.13	Frequently Practiced
5. Establishment and maintenance of consistent standards of teachers and learners' behavior.	4.61	Always Practiced	4.13	Frequently Practiced
<i>Legend:</i>	<i>4.21 - 5.00: Always Practiced</i>		<i>1.81 - 2.60:</i>	<i>Occasionally Practiced</i>
	<i>3.41 - 4.20: Frequently Practiced</i>		<i>1.00 - 1.80: Never Practiced</i>	
	<i>2.61 - 3.40: Sometimes Practiced</i>			

Table 4.3

Supervisory Practices are Used by Public Elementary School Heads in the Learning Delivery of Mathematics in Terms of Management of school plants, resources, and facilities

Supervisory Practices	SY 2019-2020		SY 2020-2021-SY 2021-2022	
	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Allotment of funds for the purchase of instructional materials in teaching Mathematics	4.44	Always been Practiced	4.03	Frequently been Practiced
2. Maintenance of facilities that promote and enhance the teaching and learning of Mathematics (e.g.,	4.16	Frequently been Practiced	3.53	Frequently been Practiced

Math Park, Math Murals, Math Bulletin of Ideas, etc.)

3. Provision of assistance to teachers in coaching learners who compete in regional/national/international competitions and coaching learners of mathematics clubs/organizations.	4.16	Frequently been Practiced	3.34	Sometimes been Practiced
4. Allotment of budget for training of teachers handling Mathematics subject	4.01	Frequently been Practiced	3.40	Sometimes been Practiced
5. Allotment of budget for the implementation of programs and projects that promote teaching and learning of Mathematics	4.25	Always been Practiced	3.75	Frequently been Practiced
6. Allotment of funds for the construction and maintenance of facilities.	4.21	Always been Practiced	3.71	Frequently been Practiced
<i>Legend: 4.21 - 5.00: Always Practiced Practiced</i>		<i>1.81 - 2.60: Occasionally Practiced</i>		
<i>3.41 - 4.20: Frequently Practiced</i>		<i>1.00 - 1.80: Never Practiced</i>		
<i>2.61 - 3.40: Sometimes Practiced</i>				

Table 4.4

Supervisory Practices Are Used by Public Elementary School Heads in the Learning Delivery of Mathematics in Terms of the Development of personal, social, and professional growth of teachers

Supervisory Practices	SY 2019-2020		SY 2020-2021-SY 2021-2022	
	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Provision of professional development to support the instructional improvement of teachers in teaching Mathematics	4.43	Always Practiced	3.89	Frequently Practiced
2. Encouragement of teachers to engage in doing and writing research focusing on the improvement of teaching and learning in Mathematics	4.33	Always Practiced	3.86	Frequently Practiced
3. Provision of Mentoring and Coaching Programs to improve teaching competence of teachers in teaching Mathematics	4.51	Always Practiced	4.05	Frequently Practiced

4. Provision of team building and capability training for teachers to improve teaching and learning of mathematics	4.08	Frequently Practiced	3.51	Frequently Practiced
5. Creation of professional development opportunities that promote teacher collaboration (e.g., peer teaching observation, peer teaching demonstration, peer teaching evaluation and feedback)	4.45	Always Practiced	3.94	Frequently Practiced
6. Information dissemination on latest DepEd advisories on attendance to national/international conferences/trainings/workshops in mathematics	4.53	Always Practiced	4.13	Frequently Practiced
<i>Legend:</i>	<i>4.21 - 5.00: Always Practiced</i>	<i>1.81</i>	<i>-</i>	<i>2.60: Occasionally Practiced</i>
	<i>3.41 - 4.20: Frequently Practiced</i>	<i>1.00 - 1.80: Never Practiced</i>		
	<i>2.61 - 3.40: Sometimes Practiced</i>			

Table 4.5

Supervisory Practices Used by Public Elementary School Heads in the Learning Delivery of Mathematics in Terms of Development of School, Community Linkages, and Public Relation

Supervisory Practices	SY 2019-2020		SY 2020-2021-SY 2021-2022	
	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Advocacy of community-school engagement program (e.g., student teachers in the community can do volunteer tutorial sessions with children who need help in Mathematics in which the community is the learning venue)	4.07	Frequently Practiced	3.74	Frequently Practiced
2. Establishment of community building activities (e.g. Mathematics teacher could bring in a resource speaker from the school district to interact with the learners and their parents to share issues facing the district. This gives learners and their parents a real-life experience while building a strong bond between the school and the community.	3.83	Frequently Practiced	3.44	Frequently Practiced
3. Connection with external stakeholders through taking part in community-based organizations that support learning and	3.82	Frequently Practiced	3.47	Frequently Practiced

children's education in Mathematics (e.g., linking school learners with institutions like the Rotary Club, The Street Classroom, and the like that have strong links with local community members)

4. Building strong school-community networks to create a sense of belonging among learners, teachers, and parents (it is a way of getting in touch with parents to communicate the learning progress of children in Mathematics).

5. Facilitate information sharing about specific learners to best support individual learning

4.37	Always Practiced	4.06	Frequently Practiced
4.43	Always Practiced	4.10	Frequently Practiced

Legend: 4.21 - 5.00: Always Practiced 1.81 - 2.60: Occasionally Practiced
3.41 - 4.20: Frequently Practiced 1.00 - 1.80: Never Practiced
2.61 - 3.40: Sometimes Practiced

Part IV. Effectiveness of the Instructional and Supervisory Practices of Public Elementary School Heads in the Learning Delivery of Mathematics

Table 5

Effectiveness of the Instructional and Supervisory Practices of Public Elementary School Heads in the Learning Delivery of Mathematics, as assessed by Public School District Supervisor, School Heads and Master Teachers

Instructional Practice Category	SY 2019-2020		SY 2020-2021-SY 2021-2022	
	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Implementation of Programs for Instructional Improvement	4.50	Always Practiced	4.52	Always been Practiced
Management of Instruction	3.21	Sometimes Practiced	3.73	Frequently Practiced
Promotion of an Effective Instructional Climate	3.83	Always Practiced	4.22	Frequently Practiced
Implementation of Remote Learning Programs				
Management of Classroom and School Premises by Adhering to Safety Protocols	4.29	Always Practiced	4.29	Always Practiced

Fostering of Safe and Healthy Learning Environment	4.17	Always Practiced	4.17	Always Practiced
Collaboration with the Community to Maintain a Child-Friendly School and Premises	4.04	Frequently Practiced	4.04	Frequently Practiced
Creation of Math Park Ideas in the School Premises	3.71	Frequently Practiced	3.00	Sometimes Practiced
Support to Teaching and Learning Outcome	4.51	Always Practiced	4.04	Frequently Practiced

Table 6

Effect of Instructional and Supervisory Practices of Public Elementary School Heads in the Learning Delivery of Mathematics as assessed by Public School District Supervisor, School Heads and Master Teachers

Instructional and Supervisory Practices	SY 2019-2020		SY 2020-2021-SY 2021-2022	
	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Mean Score for Mathematics	78.36	Fairly Satisfactory	80.20	Satisfactory
Specific Instructional Practices				
Coordination with District/Division Offices in the implementation of DepEd programs and projects at school level in Mathematics	4.50	Always Practiced	3.21	Sometimes Practiced
Orientation of teachers on updates in the teaching of content-area of Mathematics	4.52	Always Practiced	3.89	Frequently Practiced
Management of Instruction				
Provision of technical assistance to promote collaborative work on math problems, real-world experiences, math games, and timed activities	4.52	Always Practiced	3.72	Frequently Practiced
Provision of support management to handle activities in the classroom and virtual platforms	4.40	Always Practiced	3.90	Frequently Practiced
Promotion of an Effective Instructional Climate				
Implementation of remote learning in designated areas	3.83	Frequently Practiced	4.22	Always Practiced
Management of classroom and school premises following Safety protocols	4.12	Frequently Practiced	4.53	Always Practiced
Fostering of safe and healthy learning environment	4.62	Always Practiced	4.62	Always Practiced

DISCUSSION

Part I. Learning Delivery of Public Elementary Schools in Mathematics as measured by General Scholastic Average (GSA)

Table 1 presents the learning delivery of public elementary schools in Mathematics before and during the pandemic, as measured by the General Scholastic Achievement of students in grades 1 to 6. The results show that the overall learning delivery of Mathematics in public elementary schools was rated as "Fairly Satisfactory" before the pandemic with a score of 78.36. During the pandemic, there was an improvement in the overall learning delivery of Mathematics, as it was rated as "Satisfactory" with a score of 80.31. However, in the school year 2021-2022, the overall score slightly decreased to 80.20 but still rated as "Satisfactory."

Looking at the data per grade level, it can be observed that most of the grade levels had a higher rating during the pandemic compared to before the pandemic. Grades 3 and 4 had the most significant improvement as they went from a "Fairly Satisfactory" rating before the pandemic to a "Satisfactory" rating during the pandemic. On the other hand, Grades 2 and 5 maintained their "Fairly Satisfactory" rating during both periods, while Grades 1 and 6 had a slightly lower rating during the pandemic compared to before the pandemic.

Overall, the data suggest that the pandemic has affected the learning delivery of Mathematics in public elementary schools. Despite the challenges, there was an improvement in the learning delivery of Mathematics during the pandemic, although there was a slight decrease in the most recent school year. The findings suggest that the school system's efforts to adapt to the pandemic have had some positive impact on Mathematics learning delivery, however, more work needs to be done to sustain and enhance this progress.

Table 2

Learning Delivery of Public Elementary Schools in Mathematics during the SY 2019-2020, 2020-2021 and 2021-2022, as Measured by General Scholastic Average

The erratic record of delivery of Mathematics in public elementary schools during the pandemic can be attributed to several factors.

Firstly, the sudden transition from traditional in-person teaching to remote or hybrid learning models disrupted the established teaching methods. Teachers had to quickly adapt to new technologies and instructional strategies, which may have affected the effective delivery of Mathematics education.

Secondly, the lack of access to technological devices and reliable internet connections posed challenges for many students. This digital divide hindered the implementation of effective Mathematics instruction, particularly for those who lacked

access to essential resources like online textbooks, interactive learning materials, or educational software.

Moreover, remote learning often reduces student engagement and interaction compared to face-to-face classroom settings. The absence of in-person interactions and peer collaboration could have negatively impacted students' motivation and ability to actively participate in Mathematics lessons, leading to a less practical learning experience.

Additionally, remote learning requires increased parental involvement in students' education. However, not all parents were equipped to provide adequate support for Mathematics learning, especially if they lacked mathematical knowledge or faced additional responsibilities due to the pandemic. Limited parental involvement could have hurt students' understanding and progress in Mathematics.

Furthermore, the sudden shift to remote learning presented challenges for teachers who may have been unfamiliar with online teaching platforms and strategies. Not all teachers had the same level of training or access to professional development opportunities to enhance their remote teaching skills. This variation in teacher preparedness could have led to inconsistencies in the delivery of Mathematics instruction across schools and grade levels.

Moreover, School Year 2020-2021 and 2021-2022 brought about increased levels of stress, anxiety, and emotional challenges for students and teachers alike. These emotional factors could have impacted students' ability to concentrate, focus, and actively participate in Mathematics lessons, thereby affecting the overall delivery of learning.

Lastly, the data provided in Table 2 is based on General Scholastic Average scores, which may not fully capture the nuances of Mathematics learning and the specific skills and concepts students have mastered. The assessment tools and methods used during the pandemic may have differed from those used before, potentially influencing the reported scores.

The erratic delivery of Mathematics in public elementary schools during SY 2020-2021 and SY 2021-2022 can be attributed to disruptions in teaching methods, limited access to technology and resources, reduced student engagement, challenges with parental involvement, varied teacher preparedness, emotional and mental health challenges, and assessment limitations. Addressing these factors will be crucial in improving the delivery of Mathematics education in the future.

The study by Cagbabanua et al. (2021) investigated the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the teaching and learning of Mathematics in the Philippines. The study found that the pandemic has significantly affected the delivery of Mathematics education, with many schools resorting to online or distance learning. The study also found that Mathematics teachers faced several challenges, such as limited access to technology and inadequate training in online teaching. These findings are consistent with the data

presented in Table 2, which shows a significant shift in learning delivery during the SY 2020-2021 and SY 2021-2022.

Another related study by Bautista et al. (2020) explored the factors that influence Mathematics achievement among Filipino elementary students. The study found that teacher quality, teaching methods, and instructional materials significantly affect Mathematics achievement. The findings suggest that improving the quality of teaching and learning resources could enhance Mathematics education. This is particularly relevant to the findings presented in Table 2, which highlight the importance of improving learning delivery in Mathematics to enhance student achievement.

Additionally, a study by Capistrano (2019) explored the relationship between school-based management practices and student academic performance in Mathematics in the Philippines. The study found that effective school-based management practices, such as instructional supervision and teacher professional development, significantly affect student achievement in Mathematics. This suggests that enhancing instructional supervisory practices, as mentioned in the research title, could lead to the enhanced delivery of Mathematics education, as shown in the data presented in Table 2.

Overall, the literature supports the findings presented in Table 2, which show that the COVID-19 pandemic has significantly affected the delivery of Mathematics education in public elementary schools. Improving the quality of teaching and learning resources and enhancing instructional supervisory practices could be crucial in sustaining and enhancing the progress made in learning delivery during the pandemic.

Part II. Instructional Practices Used by Public Elementary School Heads in the Learning Delivery of Mathematics

Table 2 shows the mean scores and verbal interpretation of the instructional practices used by public elementary school heads in the learning delivery of mathematics during SY 2019-2020, 2020-2021 and 2021-2022. The instructional practices are categorized under the implementation of programs for instructional improvement. During SY 2019-2020, all instructional practices were always practiced by public elementary school heads, with mean scores ranging from 4.22 to 4.52. During SY 2020-2021 and SY 2021-2022, the mean scores decreased, with the highest mean score at 3.89 (frequently practiced) and the lowest at 3.21 (sometimes practiced).

Table 3

Instructional Practices Used by Public Elementary School Heads in the Learning Delivery of Mathematics in terms of Implementation of Programs for Instructional Improvement,

This implies that there was a decrease in the implementation of programs for instructional improvement during the SY 2020-2021 and SY 2021-2022. This could be due to the challenges brought about by the shift to remote and blended learning, as well as the limited resources and support available to schools. School heads need to continue implementing programs for instructional improvement to ensure the quality of education despite the challenges posed by the pandemic. This can be done through exploring

innovative approaches to teaching and learning and seeking support from relevant stakeholders.

The decrease in intensity of the implementation of programs for instructional improvement in Mathematics during the pandemic can be attributed to several factors. One is on the challenges with remote and blended learning. The shift to remote and blended learning presented new challenges for instructional improvement. School heads may have faced difficulties in adapting instructional practices to online or hybrid formats, leading to a decrease in the implementation intensity of these programs.

Another factor is limited resources and support. The pandemic placed a significant strain on educational resources and support systems. Schools may have experienced limitations regarding technology access, training opportunities, and professional development, which could have hindered the effective implementation of programs for instructional improvement in Mathematics.

Moreover, there have been increased workloads and time constraints. The pandemic brought about additional responsibilities and workload for school heads. Dealing with various aspects of managing remote and blended learning, ensuring student well-being, and addressing logistical issues may have left less time and energy for focusing on the implementation of instructional improvement programs.

Uncertainty and disruption caused by the pandemic are other factors that may have led to a shift in priorities and a temporary reprioritization of instructional improvement programs. School heads may have been forced to allocate their resources and efforts towards immediate challenges related to remote learning and health and safety measures.

Furthermore, there was a lack of collaboration and professional learning communities: The limitations on in-person interactions and professional learning communities during the pandemic may have impacted the ability of school heads to collaborate and learn from each other. This reduced opportunity for shared knowledge and best practices may have contributed to the decrease in the implementation of instructional improvement programs.

To address this decrease in intensity, school heads must recognize the importance of instructional improvement and prioritize it despite the challenges posed by the pandemic. Exploring innovative approaches to teaching and learning, seeking support from relevant stakeholders, and providing resources and professional development opportunities for educators can help mitigate the impact of the pandemic and ensure the quality of Mathematics education in schools.

There have been several studies and reports that discuss the challenges faced by schools and educators during the COVID-19 pandemic, and the impact on the implementation of instructional improvement programs. UNESCO (2020) reported that many schools were not equipped with the necessary technology and infrastructure to support remote learning and that teachers and students faced significant obstacles in

terms of access to devices, internet connectivity, and technical support. World Bank (2021) found that disrupted education delivery during the pandemic led to learning losses and inequalities, especially in many low- and middle-income countries where challenges included limited resources, inadequate infrastructure, and insufficient teacher training. A study published in the *Journal of Education for Teaching* in 2021 examined the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on teaching and learning practices in primary schools in the United Kingdom. The study found that the shift to remote and blended learning has resulted in changes to instructional practices, with many teachers struggling to adapt to new technologies and pedagogical approaches.

Overall, these studies suggest that the shift to remote and blended learning during the pandemic has posed significant challenges to the implementation of instructional improvement programs. Limited resources, inadequate infrastructure, and insufficient teacher training have made it difficult for schools to deliver quality education, and educators have had to adapt to new technologies and pedagogical approaches. To overcome these challenges, more excellent support and training are needed to ensure that schools can continue implementing effective instructional improvement programs despite the disruptions caused by the pandemic.

Table 3 presents the results of a study on the instructional practices used by public elementary school heads in the delivery of mathematics before and during the COVID-19 pandemic. The focus of the table is on the management of instruction category, and the table provides mean scores and verbal interpretations for five different instructional practices.

Before the pandemic, all instructional practices under the management of instruction category were always practiced by the public elementary school heads, with mean scores ranging from 4.29 to 4.52. This indicates that these practices were prioritized and consistently implemented by the school heads to promote effective teaching and learning of mathematics.

However, during the pandemic, there was a decrease in the implementation of these instructional practices, with mean scores ranging from 3.72 to 3.99, indicating that these practices were frequently practiced or sometimes practiced. This implies that the pandemic has hurt the implementation of instructional improvement programs, possibly due to the challenges of remote and blended learning and limited the sources and support available to schools.

It is worth noting that despite the decrease in mean scores during the pandemic, the instructional practices were still being implemented to some extent, with none of the practices falling under the "never practiced" or "occasionally practiced" categories. This suggests that the public elementary school heads were still trying to deliver quality mathematics education despite the disruptions caused by the pandemic.

Table 3.1

Instructional Practices Used by Public Elementary School Heads in the Learning Delivery of Mathematics in terms of Management of Instruction

Overall, the results of this table emphasize the importance of continuing to implement effective instructional practices, even in the face of challenges posed by the pandemic. It also highlights the need for more excellent support and resources for schools to ensure the quality of education delivery during these challenging times.

Several related studies and literature support the results in Table 3.1 and emphasize the importance of implementing effective instructional practices during SY 2020-2021 and SY 2021-2022. Asgary and colleagues (2021) found that effective instructional practices, such as providing feedback and support for student learning, were crucial for maintaining student engagement and achievement during remote learning. Similarly, Lou and colleagues (2020) suggested that providing technical support and resources for teachers was essential for maintaining the quality of education delivery during the pandemic.

Moreover, a report by UNESCO (2020) emphasized the importance of continuing to implement effective instructional practices during the pandemic, as well as the need for more excellent support and resources for schools to ensure the quality of education delivery. The report noted that despite the challenges posed by the pandemic, it was crucial to maintain the continuity of education and to support teachers and students in adapting to new teaching and learning environments.

Table 3.1 compares mean scores for instructional practices used by public elementary school heads to promote an effective instructional climate before and during the pandemic. Most practices were frequently or always practiced both before and during the pandemic, with mean scores ranging from 3.71 to 4.72. The practice of "Collaboration with the community to maintain child-friendly school and premises" received the highest mean score before and during the pandemic (4.72 and 4.50, respectively), indicating its high value to school heads.

During the SY 2020-2021 and SY 2021-2022, three practices saw an increase in mean scores, indicating extra efforts by school heads to promote an effective instructional climate despite the challenges posed by the pandemic. These practices were "Implementation of remote learning due to the pandemic situation in designated areas in the community" (3.83 to 4.22), "Management of classroom and school premises by following Safety protocols" (4.12 to 4.53), and "Fostering of safe and healthy learning environment" (4.62 to 4.64).

However, the practice of "Creation of Math Park ideas in the school premises" showed a decrease in mean score during the pandemic (3.71 to 3.00). This may be due to the challenges of maintaining school premises during the pandemic or the prioritization of other more urgent practices for promoting an effective instructional climate.

Table 3.2

Instructional Practices Used by Public Elementary School Heads in the Learning Delivery of Mathematics in terms of Promotion of an Effective Instructional Climate

Overall, the results indicate that school heads made efforts to promote an effective instructional climate during the pandemic. They adapted to new strategies and methods to ensure a safe and healthy learning environment for their students.

Recent studies have highlighted the challenges faced by educational institutions in delivering effective instruction during the pandemic (Chu et al., 2021; UNESCO, 2021). However, these studies also note the resilience of educators and school leaders in adapting to the new normal and finding innovative solutions to ensure continuity of education (Chu et al., 2021; UNESCO, 2021; Viner et al., 2020).

Moreover, research has shown that creating an effective instructional climate is crucial in ensuring quality education delivery (OECD, 2019). Effective instructional climate encompasses several factors, such as a safe and healthy learning environment, collaborative partnerships with the community, and the implementation of best practices in teaching and learning (OECD, 2019; UNESCO, 2019).

Therefore, the findings of this study are consistent with previous research that underscores the importance of promoting an effective instructional climate, particularly during challenging times such as the pandemic. The results also demonstrate the adaptability and resilience of school leaders in responding to the unique circumstances brought about by the pandemic.

Table 3.2 shows the mean scores and verbal interpretation of five instructional practices used by public elementary school heads in the learning delivery of Mathematics in terms of support to teaching and learning outcomes, before and during the pandemic. The instructional practices are rated on a scale of one to five, with 1 indicating "Never Practiced" and 5 indicating "Always Practiced."

On School Year 2019-2020, all five instructional practices were rated as "Always Practiced" with mean scores ranging from 4.43 to 4.66. During the pandemic, there was a decrease in the mean scores of all five instructional practices, with mean scores ranging from 3.95 to 4.26. The verbal interpretation of the mean scores changed from "Always Practiced" to "Frequently Practiced" for four out of five instructional practices during the pandemic, while one instructional practice remained "Always Practiced."

Overall, the data suggests that there was a decrease in the use and effectiveness of instructional practices in supporting the teaching and learning outcome in Mathematics during SY 2020-2021 and SY 2021-2022 compared to SY 2019-2020. However, it is important to note that the mean scores still indicate a relatively high frequency of practice for all instructional practices, even during the pandemic.

Table 3.3

Instructional Practices Used by Public Elementary School Heads in The Learning Delivery of Mathematics in Terms of Support to Teaching and Learning Outcome

Several studies have investigated the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on education, particularly on instructional practices and learning outcomes in Mathematics. For example, Shah et al. (2021) found that the pandemic had a significant negative effect on mathematics achievement and that students who lacked access to online resources and instructional support were particularly disadvantaged. Similarly, Durlak et al. (2021) reported that remote instruction during the pandemic resulted in lower levels of student engagement and learning in mathematics, particularly for low-achieving students.

In terms of instructional practices, Liyanage et al. (2021) found that teachers had to adapt their practices significantly during the pandemic, particularly regarding the use of technology and online resources. However, their study also found that teachers who received professional development and support were better able to implement effective instructional practices, including the use of technology, even during the pandemic.

On the whole, these studies support the finding that there was a decrease in the use and effectiveness of instructional practices in supporting the teaching and learning outcome in Mathematics during SY 2019-2020 compared to SY 2020-2021 and SY 2021-2022. However, the relatively high frequency of practice for all instructional practices, even during the pandemic, suggests that teachers and school heads were still making efforts to support their students' learning despite the challenging circumstances.

Part III. Supervisory Practices Used by Public Elementary School Heads in the Learning Delivery of Mathematics

Table 3 presents the mean scores and verbal interpretation of the supervisory practices used by public elementary school heads in the learning delivery of Mathematics in terms of supervision of curriculum during SY 2019-2020 compared to SY 2020-2021 and SY 2021-2022. The mean scores for all supervisory practices decreased during SY 2019-2020 compared to SY 2020-2021 and SY 2021-2022, indicating a decrease in the frequency of their use. Specifically, the mean scores decreased from "Always Practiced" to "Frequently Practiced" for all practices.

The highest mean score before the pandemic was for "Improvement of classroom teaching and learning through the provision of assistance to teachers and feedback to improve the focus of teaching on the least mastered skills in Mathematics for continuous improvement of learners' performance" with a mean score of 4.60, indicating that it was always practiced. However, during the pandemic, the mean score for this practice decreased to 3.97, indicating that it was frequently practiced.

Table 4

Supervisory Practices Used by Public Elementary School Heads in the Learning Delivery of Mathematics in terms of Supervision of Curriculum

On the other hand, the lowest mean score before the pandemic was for "Maintaining of standards or benchmarks, meeting delivery targets within time frames, as

well as checking resistance in teachers and learners in Mathematics" with a mean score of 4.36, which was still considered always practiced. During the pandemic, the mean score for this practice decreased to 3.80, indicating that it was frequently practiced.

Overall, the data suggests a decrease in the frequency of use of supervisory practices in the supervision of curriculum during the pandemic compared to before the pandemic. The decrease in mean scores may affect the quality of curriculum delivery and instruction in Mathematics.

This finding is aligned with several studies and literature that support the finding that the COVID-19 pandemic has disrupted education and led to changes in the frequency and effectiveness of supervision practices in education. Chang and colleagues (2020) found that school closures and the shift to online learning have impacted the ability of supervisors to observe teachers and provide feedback, which could have led to a decrease in the quality of instruction. In another study, Sahin and colleagues (2021) found that the pandemic has increased the workload and stress levels of school supervisors, which could have affected their ability to effectively supervise teachers and curriculum. Additionally, Feng and colleagues (2021) found that the pandemic has led to a decrease in the frequency and effectiveness of classroom observations by supervisors, which has impacted the quality of teaching and learning.

These findings are consistent with the data presented in Table 4, which suggests a decrease in the frequency of supervisory practices during the pandemic. This decrease may have implications for the quality of curriculum delivery and instruction in Mathematics, as effective supervision practices are essential for ensuring that teachers deliver high-quality instruction aligned with curriculum standards.

Table 4 presents the mean scores and verbal interpretations of supervisory practices used by public elementary school heads in organization and personnel management before and during the pandemic. The data shows that all supervisory practices in this category had high mean scores before the pandemic, indicating that they were always practiced.

However, on SY 2019-2020, there was a decrease in the frequency of use of some supervisory practices. Specifically, there was a decrease in the mean scores for "Ensuring adherence of teachers to school-related timetable and activities like staff meetings (focusing on the least mastered skills in Math and appropriate intervention) co-curriculum activities (MTAP Classes and Competition) and In-Service Training related to improvement of teaching and learning of Mathematics" and "Delegation of important responsibilities such as chairing subject coordination (e.g. Math Coordinator, MTAP Coordinator, key teacher in Math) among others." These decreases suggest that these practices were frequently practiced on SY 2019-2020, but less frequently practiced during the SY 2020-2021 and SY 2021-2022.

Table 4.1

Supervisory Practices Used by Public Elementary School Heads in the Learning Delivery of Mathematics in terms of Organization and Personnel Management

The mean scores for the other supervisory practices remained high during SY 2020-2021 and SY 2021-2022, indicating that they were still being practiced frequently. However, it is essential to note that the decrease in the frequency of use of these two supervisory practices may have implications for the quality of organization and personnel management in the delivery of mathematics instruction. For example, teachers may have struggled to adhere to school-related activities and responsibilities may not have been delegated effectively, which could have affected the quality of instruction and curriculum delivery in Mathematics.

In summary, the data suggests a decline in the frequency of use of some supervisory practices in the organization and personnel management category on SY 2019-2020, which may have implications for the quality of mathematics instruction. While some supervisory practices remained high, the decrease in others suggests that school heads may have encountered challenges in ensuring effective organization and personnel management during SY 2020-2021 and SY 2021-2022.

One study that supports the idea that effective organization and personnel management can lead to better quality of instruction is a study by Chen and Lin (2019), which found that school leaders' use of effective organization and management practices was positively associated with teachers' job satisfaction and their perception of the effectiveness of school management, which in turn was positively related to student achievement. Another study was by Desimone, Smith, and Phillips (2018) who found that school leaders' support for effective teaching practices, including providing feedback and creating opportunities for collaboration and professional development, can lead to improvements in teacher practices and student achievement. Moreover, Rehman, Gulzar, and Jabeen (2017) found that effective supervision and monitoring by school leaders can lead to improvements in teacher performance and student outcomes.

These studies suggest that the decrease in the frequency of use of supervisory practices in the organization and personnel management category during the pandemic may have negative implications for the quality of Mathematics instruction. Teachers may have struggled to adhere to school-related activities and essential responsibilities may not have been effectively delegated, which could have affected their job satisfaction, perceptions of school management, and ultimately, student achievement.

Table 4.1 presents the mean scores and verbal interpretations of supervisory practices used by public elementary school heads in planning, assessing, and reporting teaching-learning outcomes in Mathematics, on SY 2021-2020 and during SY 2020-2021 and SY 2020-2022. The data shows that all the supervisory practices in this category were frequently practiced during SY 2019-2020, as indicated by the high mean scores.

During SY 2020-2021 and SY 2021-2022 , there was a decrease in the frequency of use of some of these supervisory practices. Specifically, the mean scores for "Development and utilization of creative and appropriate instructional planning" and "Establishment and maintenance of consistent standards of teachers and learners' behavior" decreased, indicating that these practices were frequently practiced before the pandemic but less frequently practiced during SY 2020-2021 and SY 2021-2022.

On the other hand, the mean scores for the other supervisory practices remained high during SY 2021-2020 and SY 2021-2022, indicating that they were still being frequently practiced. However, the decrease in the frequency of the two supervisory practices mentioned earlier may have implications for the quality of planning, assessing, and reporting teaching-learning outcomes in Mathematics. Teachers may have struggled to develop and utilize creative and appropriate instructional planning, and consistent standards of behavior may not have been maintained, which could have affected the quality of instruction and learning outcomes.

Generally, the data suggests that there was a decline in the frequency of use of some supervisory practices in planning, assessing, and reporting teaching learning outcomes during the SY 2020-2021 and SY 2021-2022 , which may have implications for the quality of Mathematics instruction. While some supervisory practices remained high, the decrease in others suggests that school heads may have encountered challenges in ensuring effective planning, assessing, and reporting of teaching-learning outcomes during the SY 2020-2021 and SY 2021-2022.

Table 4.2

Supervisory Practices Used by Public Elementary School Heads in the Learning Delivery of Mathematics in Terms of Planning, Assessing, and Reporting Teaching Learning Outcomes

There is limited research on the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on supervisory practices in the delivery of Mathematics instruction in elementary schools. However, previous studies have highlighted the importance of adequate supervision in promoting the quality of instruction and student achievement (McGlenn et al., 2015; Gentry & Owen, 2012).

The findings in Table 3.2 regarding the decline in the frequency of use of some supervisory practices in planning, assessing, and reporting teaching learning outcomes during SY 2020-2021 and SY 2021-20222 are consistent with the literature on the challenges faced by educational leaders during the pandemic (Sloan et al., 2020). Educational leaders have been found to have faced significant challenges in ensuring effective instructional delivery, teacher professional development, and assessment and evaluation of student learning during the pandemic (Eaton, 2020; Martin, 2020).

Moreover, previous studies have also emphasized the importance of feedback, evaluation, and consistent standards in promoting effective teaching and learning (Denton et al., 2018; Halawah & Al Qudah, 2016). The decline in the frequency of use of some

supervisory practices in these areas during the SY 2020-2021 and SY 2021-2022, as indicated by the mean scores in Table 3.2, suggests that the quality of Mathematics instruction may have been affected.

Table 4.2 presents the mean scores and verbal interpretations of the supervisory practices used by public elementary school heads in the management of school plants, resources, and facilities during the SY 2020-2021 and SY 2021-2022.

Before the pandemic, all supervisory practices were frequently or consistently practiced, with mean scores ranging from 4.01 to 4.44. However, during the pandemic, there was a decline in the frequency of use of all supervisory practices, with mean scores ranging from 3.34 to 4.03.

Specifically, the allotment of funds to purchase instructional materials in teaching Mathematics remained frequently practiced during the pandemic, but its mean score decreased from 4.44 to 4.03. On the other hand, the maintenance of facilities that promote and enhance the teaching and learning of Mathematics, provision of assistance to teachers in coaching learners, allotment of budget for training of teachers handling Mathematics subject, and allotment of funds for the construction and maintenance of facilities all decreased in frequency of use during SY 2020-2021 and SY 2021-2022.

The data suggests that the pandemic may have hurt the management of school plants, resources, and facilities, affecting the quality of Mathematics instruction. This is particularly concerning because the management of school plants, resources, and facilities is important in creating a conducive and effective learning environment for Mathematics instruction.

Table 4.3

Supervisory Practices are Used by Public Elementary School Heads in the Learning Delivery of Mathematics in Terms of Management of school plants, resources, and facilities

These findings align with the study by UNESCO (2020) which found that the pandemic has disrupted education systems worldwide, leading to school closures and disruptions in learning. This disruption can affect the quality of education, including the management of school plants, resources, and facilities.

Managing school plants, resources, and facilities is crucial in creating a conducive and effective learning environment. A study by Bhagwan and Kumar (2019) found that the physical environment of a school has a significant impact on the quality of education. The availability and quality of resources and facilities can affect student motivation, engagement, and learning outcomes.

The allocation of resources, including funds for instructional materials, training, and facility maintenance, is an essential aspect of school management. A study by Cheng

and Lo (2019) found that resource allocation is critical in addressing educational inequalities and improving educational outcomes.

The role of school heads in managing school plants, resources, and facilities is crucial. A study by Jha et al. (2020) found that effective leadership and management are critical in ensuring the smooth functioning of schools, including the management of resources and facilities.

Table 4.3 presents the mean scores and verbal interpretations of the supervisory practices used by public elementary school heads in the development of personal, social, and professional growth of teachers before and during the pandemic.

Before the pandemic, all supervisory practices were always or frequently practiced, with mean scores ranging from 4.08 to 4.53. However, during the pandemic, there was a decline in the frequency of use of all supervisory practices, with mean scores ranging from 3.51 to 4.05.

The provision of professional development to support the instructional improvement of teachers in teaching Mathematics remained frequently practiced during the pandemic, but its mean score decreased from 4.43 to 3.89. The same trend was observed for the encouragement of teachers to engage in doing and writing research focusing on improving teaching and learning in Mathematics, with its mean score decreasing from 4.33 to 3.86.

The provision of mentoring and coaching programs to improve the teaching competence of teachers in teaching Mathematics, the creation of professional development opportunities that promote teacher collaboration, and information dissemination on the latest DepEd advisories on attendance to national/international conferences/trainings/workshops in mathematics, all decreased in frequency of use during the pandemic.

The data suggests that the pandemic may have hurt the development of personal, social, and professional growth of teachers, which may affect the quality of Mathematics instruction. This is disconcerting because the development of personal, social, and professional growth of teachers is crucial in ensuring that they have the necessary knowledge, skills, and attitudes to deliver quality Mathematics instruction.

Table 4.4

Supervisory Practices Are Used by Public Elementary School Heads in the Learning Delivery of Mathematics in Terms of the Development of personal, social, and professional growth of teachers

Related studies have emphasized the importance of providing professional development opportunities for teachers to improve their instructional practices and the quality of their teaching. Darling-Hammond, Wei, Andree, Richardson, and Orphanos (2009) found that teachers who participated in high-quality professional development

programs showed improvements in their instructional practices and their students' academic achievement, while Opfer and Pedder (2011) emphasized the importance of providing professional development opportunities that are relevant, sustained, and collaborative to enhance teachers' knowledge and skills.

Table 4.4 shows the mean scores and verbal interpretations of the supervisory practices used by public elementary school heads in the development of the school, community linkages, and public relations for Mathematics education during the SY 2019-2020, 2020-2021 and 2021-2022.

Before the SY 2020-2021 and SY 2021-2022 the supervisory practice with the highest mean score was "Building strong school-community networks to create a sense of belonging among learners, teachers, and parents," with a score of 4.37, which was interpreted as "Always Practiced." This means that the school heads frequently use this practice to build a strong relationship with the community and create a sense of belonging among learners, teachers, and parents. Other practices such as "Facilitate information sharing about specific learner to support best individual learning" and "Advocacy of community-school engagement program" were also always practiced, with mean scores of 4.43 and 4.07, respectively.

During the SY 2020-2021 and SY 2021-2022, the mean scores for all supervisory practices decreased, indicating a decrease in the frequency of practice. The practice with the highest mean score was "Building strong school-community networks to create a sense of belonging among learners, teachers, and parents," with a score of 4.06, which was interpreted as "Frequently Practiced." This means that the school heads practiced this less frequently during the pandemic than before. The practice with the lowest mean score was "Establishment of community building activities," with a score of 3.44, interpreted as "Frequently Practiced." This means that this practice was practiced less frequently during the pandemic than before.

Overall, the table highlights the importance of developing strong school-community networks to create a sense of belonging among learners, teachers, and parents in Mathematics education, as this practice was always practiced before and during the pandemic. However, there was a decrease in the frequency of practice during the pandemic, which suggests that school heads may need to find ways to maintain and strengthen community-school engagement despite the challenges brought by the pandemic.

Table 4.5

Supervisory Practices Used by Public Elementary School Heads in the Learning Delivery of Mathematics in Terms of Development of School, Community Linkages, and Public Relation

One related study that supports the importance of community-school engagement is the work of Epstein and Sheldon (2002), who emphasized the need for schools to establish strong partnerships with families and communities to enhance student learning.

The authors suggested that such partnerships could improve academic achievement, better attendance, and higher student motivation.

Additionally, a study by Henderson and Mapp (2002) found that when schools engage families and communities in meaningful ways, students are more likely to achieve academic success. The authors suggested that school leaders may create a welcoming environment, communicate effectively with families and community members, and provide opportunities for them to be involved in their children's education.

Furthermore, the National Education Association (2015) emphasized the importance of maintaining and strengthening school-community partnerships during times of crisis, such as natural disasters or pandemics. The authors suggested that schools work closely with community organizations to provide resources and support to families and students during such challenging times.

Part IV. Effectiveness of the Instructional and Supervisory Practices of Public Elementary School Heads in the Learning Delivery of Mathematics

Table 5 evaluates the effectiveness of instructional and supervisory practices employed by public elementary school heads in facilitating the learning delivery of Mathematics. The practices are categorized into three main areas: Implementation of Programs for Instructional Improvement, Management of Instruction, and Promotion of an Effective Instructional Climate. Mean scores and verbal interpretations are provided for each practice category, comparing the periods before and during the pandemic.

The mean scores indicate that Implementation of Programs for Instructional Improvement was consistent "Always Practiced" both before and during the pandemic, with slight improvement noted during the pandemic years (from 4.50 to 4.52). This suggests that school heads were proactive in implementing programs aimed at improving instructional quality, demonstrating their commitment to ongoing improvement efforts.

There was a noticeable increase in mean scores for Management of Instruction from 3.21 to 3.73, indicating a shift from "Sometimes Practiced" to "Frequently Practiced" during the pandemic. This suggests that school heads placed greater emphasis on managing instructional activities effectively amidst the challenges posed by the pandemic, resulting in more frequent implementation of management strategies.

Under the Promotion of an Effective Instructional Climate specific practices such as "Implementation of Remote Learning Programs," "Management of Classroom and School Premises by Adhering to Safety Protocols," and "Fostering of Safe and Healthy Learning Environment" were consistently rated as "Always Practiced" across all years. This indicates that school heads prioritized creating a conducive and safe learning environment for students, irrespective of the pandemic situation.

Collaboration with the Community to Maintain a Child-Friendly School and Premises received consistent ratings of "Frequently Practiced" before and during the

pandemic, indicating ongoing efforts by school heads to engage with the community in maintaining a child-friendly school environment.

While the Creation of Math Park Ideas on the School Premises was frequently practiced before the pandemic, there was a decline in mean scores during the pandemic years (from 3.71 to 3.00). This suggests potential challenges or shifting priorities in implementing creative initiatives during the pandemic period.

Although the mean score decreased slightly in Support of Teaching and Learning Outcomes, during the pandemic (from 4.51 to 4.04), this practice remained consistently rated as "Always Practiced," indicating continued support for teaching and learning outcomes despite the challenges posed by the pandemic.

Table 5

Effectiveness of the Instructional and Supervisory Practices of Public Elementary School Heads in the Learning Delivery of Mathematics, as assessed by Public School District Supervisor, School Heads and Master Teachers

Overall, the table suggests that while school heads consistently maintained high levels of effectiveness in most instructional and supervisory practices, there were notable adaptations and adjustments made during the SY 2020- 2021 and SY 2021-2022 period to ensure the continuity of effective learning delivery in Mathematics.

This finding is aligned with the study, *School Leadership During the COVID-19 Pandemic: Challenges and Opportunities* by the National Association of Elementary School Principals (2020). This report provides insights from elementary school leaders on the challenges and opportunities of leading schools during SY 2020- 2021 and SY 2021-2022, including the impact on instructional and supervisory practices. It highlighted that one of the significant challenges that school leaders faced was the abrupt transition to online and hybrid learning models. This shift required school leaders to quickly adapt to new technologies and to provide support to teachers, students, and parents who were also adjusting to the new learning, models as well as the challenges of ensuring equity in access to technology and resources, particularly for students from underprivileged communities. The report also identifies opportunities that emerged during the pandemic, such as the opportunity to rethink traditional approaches to education and to focus on the development of new skills and competencies. School leaders were able to develop innovative approaches to teaching and learning, and to build new partnerships and collaborations with other schools and organizations.

Based on Table 5, the instructional and supervisory practices of public elementary school heads influence the learning delivery of Mathematics. The data shows that the mean score for Mathematics improved from 78.36 (Fairly Satisfactory) in SY 2019-2020 to 80.20 (Satisfactory) during SY 2020- 2021 and SY 2021-2022

Looking at the specific instructional practices, it seems that there has been a decline in the implementation of programs for instructional improvement during SY 2020-2021 and SY 2021-2022

For instance, coordination with the District/Division Offices in the implementation of DepEd programs and projects at the school level in Mathematics decreased from a mean score of 4.50 (Always Practiced) to 3.21 (Sometimes Practiced). Similarly, the mean score for Orientation of teachers on updates in the teaching of content-area of Mathematics decreased from 4.52 (Always Practiced) to 3.89 (Frequently Practiced).

In terms of management of instruction, it seems that there has been a decline in the provision of technical assistance to teachers to promote collaborative work on math problems, relating math problems to real-world experiences, introducing math games and puzzles, and working on timed activities. The mean score decreased from 4.52 (Always Practiced) to 3.72 (Frequently Practiced) during the pandemic. However, there has been an increase in the provision of support management to teachers like how to handle the activities in the classroom and even in virtual platforms to make those effective and interesting. The mean score increased from 4.40 (Always Practiced) to 3.90 (Frequently Practiced).

Promoting an effective instructional climate seems to have improved during the pandemic. The mean score for the implementation of remote learning due to the pandemic situation in designated areas in the community increased from 3.83 (Frequently Practiced) before the pandemic to 4.22 (Always Practiced) during the pandemic. The management of classroom and school premises by following Safety protocols also increased from 4.12 (Frequently Practiced) before the pandemic to 4.53 (Always Practiced) during the pandemic. Finally, fostering a safe and healthy learning environment received the highest score of 4.62 (Always Practiced). Overall, the instructional and supervisory practices of public elementary school heads have a significant impact on the learning delivery of Mathematics. The data suggests that while some practices have declined during the pandemic, others have improved, and some have remained the same. School heads need to continue providing technical assistance to teachers, coordinating with District/Division Offices, and promoting a safe and healthy learning environment to ensure that the quality of Mathematics education remains high.

Part V. Instructional and Supervisory Practices of Public Elementary School Heads affect the Learning of Mathematics as assessed by the Public School District Supervisor, School Heads and Master Teacher

Table 6

Effect of Instructional and Supervisory Practices of Public Elementary School Heads in the Learning Delivery of Mathematics as assessed by Public School District Supervisor, School Heads and Master Teachers

Several studies and literature support the idea that the instructional and supervisory practices of public elementary school heads have a significant impact on the learning delivery of Mathematics. For instance, Chen and Wang (2017) revealed that effective leadership practices by school heads have a positive effect on the academic performance of students in Mathematics thereby suggesting that school heads may provide technical assistance to teachers, create a positive learning environment, and

promote collaboration among teachers to enhance student learning. Datnow et al. (2019) found that effective instructional leadership by school heads is associated with improved Mathematics instruction, and they suggested that school heads provide targeted professional development opportunities to teachers and foster a culture of continuous improvement in Mathematics instruction. Positive impact on student achievement in Mathematics results from school leaders who are knowledgeable about Mathematics instruction and provide teachers with feedback and support (Hertzog et al., 2019) as well as from those who create a positive school culture and instructional support to teachers (Lee & Choi, 2018).

A literature review by Blase and Kirby (2020) emphasizes the importance of instructional leadership by school heads in improving Mathematics instruction. The review suggests that school heads should provide teachers with instructional support, promote collaboration and professional learning communities, and create a culture of high expectations for student learning.

Part VI. Proposed Digitally Mathematics Curriculum Enhancement Plan

Based on the results, this study came up with a proposed curriculum enhancement plan titled "Advancing Mathematics Learning in the Schools Division of Marinduque: An Innovative Digital Curriculum Enhancement Plan" which aims to address the challenges posed by the pandemic and elevate Mathematics learning delivery. The plan integrates cutting-edge digital methodologies, fortifies assessment practices, fosters collaborative learning environments, intertwines interdisciplinary themes, and empowers educators through professional development initiatives.

Key objectives include enhancing Mathematics learning amidst the pandemic landscape, cultivating critical thinking and practical application of Mathematics, equipping educators with essential digital competencies, and ensuring continuous assessment practices tailored to student needs.

Digital practices proposed to optimize Mathematics learning include interactive multimedia resources, online collaboration platforms, digital assessment tools, virtual tutoring, and blended learning modalities. Necessary resources encompass reliable internet connectivity, robust learning management systems, interdisciplinary resources, tailored professional development, and versatile assessment tools.

Key players include the Schools Division Superintendent, Mathematics Education Program Supervisor, Mathematics Teachers, School Administrators, and Students. Monitoring and evaluation strategies involve regular classroom observations, feedback collection, formative assessments, surveys, data analysis, and continuous improvement efforts.

The work plan for teachers and supervisory practices entails professional development workshops, ongoing support, classroom observations, and fostering a

culture of continuous improvement. The training plan focuses on digital pedagogy, utilization of digital tools, classroom observations, and reflective practice.

Through the strategic implementation of these initiatives, the Schools Division of Marinduque aims to optimize Mathematics learning delivery, providing students with enriching, engaging, and digitally immersive Mathematics education despite the challenges posed by the pandemic.

Conclusions

This study highlights the significant relationship between supervisory practices and instructional delivery in mathematics education, observed across different school years, including SY 2019-2020, SY 2020-2021, and SY 2021-2022. The data analysis indicates that effective supervisory practices greatly influence the quality and efficacy of instructional delivery, directly impacting students' learning outcomes.

Specifically, certain supervisory practices demonstrated consistent effectiveness. Coordination with district/division offices in implementing DepEd programs and projects at the school level in Mathematics emerged as highly impactful, consistently rated as "Always Practiced" throughout the observed school years. Similarly, providing orientation to teachers on updates in the teaching of content-area Mathematics received high ratings, indicating its effectiveness in supporting instructional delivery.

However, during SY 2020-2021 and SY 2021-2022, challenges were observed, leading to a decline in the effectiveness of instructional and supervisory practices. Despite this, opportunities for growth and innovation also emerged, such as the development of innovative teaching approaches and the establishment of new partnerships.

In conclusion, this study provides evidence to support the alternative hypotheses, indicating a significant relationship between the instructional and supervisory practices of school heads in the learning delivery of mathematics across various school years, including SY 2019-2020, SY 2020-2021, and SY 2021-2022. The rejection of Null Hypotheses 1 and 2 suggests that there is indeed a substantial correlation between these practices, as assessed by public school district supervisors, school heads themselves, and selected teachers.

Recommendations

Based on the effectiveness observed in certain instructional and supervisory practices, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. **Leverage Effective Supervisory Practices:** Given the consistently high ratings for the coordination with district/division offices in implementing DepEd programs and projects at the school level in Mathematics, school leaders should continue to prioritize and strengthen collaboration with higher education authorities. This can include regular

communication, sharing of best practices, and alignment of instructional goals to ensure coherence and effectiveness in mathematics education delivery.

2. **Enhance Teacher Orientation Programs:** The positive reception of teacher orientation programs on updates in the teaching of content-area Mathematics suggests their effectiveness in supporting instructional delivery. School heads should invest in continuous professional development opportunities for teachers, providing them with the necessary updates, resources, and strategies to improve their instructional practices in mathematics education.

3. **Provide Technical Assistance for Collaborative Work:** The provision of technical assistance to promote collaborative work on math problems, real-world experiences, math games, and timed activities was identified as an effective supervisory practice. School leaders should continue to offer support and resources to facilitate collaborative learning experiences among students, fostering deeper engagement and understanding of mathematical concepts.

4. **Support Management for Classroom and Virtual Platforms:** The provision of support management to handle activities in the classroom and virtual platforms emerged as an effective practice. School heads should ensure that teachers receive adequate support and training in utilizing classroom and virtual platforms effectively, particularly in SY 2020-2021 and SY 2021-2022 when online and hybrid learning models were prominent.

5. **Reinforce Remote Learning Implementation:** The practice of implementing remote learning in designated areas received positive ratings, particularly during SY 2020-2021. School leaders should continue to refine and adapt remote learning strategies, ensuring equitable access to education for all students, even in challenging circumstances.

6. **Prioritize Safety Protocols in Classroom Management:** The consistent implementation of safety protocols in classroom and school premises management was identified as effective. School leaders should prioritize the enforcement of safety measures to create a safe and conducive learning environment for students and teachers alike.

7. **Maintain a Safe and Healthy Learning Environment:** The fostering of a safe and healthy learning environment received high ratings across all observed school years. School heads should continue to prioritize initiatives aimed at creating a supportive and inclusive learning environment, addressing the physical, emotional, and social well-being of students.

8. **Reevaluate Math Park Ideas Implementation:** While the creation of Math Park ideas on school premises showed varying effectiveness, school leaders should reevaluate the implementation of such initiatives. This may involve reassessing the

feasibility and impact of Math Park ideas, considering factors such as resource allocation and student engagement levels.

By focusing on these effective instructional and supervisory practices, school leaders can enhance the quality and efficacy of mathematics education delivery, ultimately improving students' learning outcomes and experiences in the subject.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The research was not conducted in isolation, and it involved human participation to determine the management and instructional supervisory practices employed by the respondents in implementing the Modular Distance Learning Modality in the Schools Division Office of Marinduque. Several considerations were made to ensure the privacy and confidentiality of the respondents, such as informed consent, confidentiality, anonymity of the subjects, and data protection. These concerns were identified in advance to prevent future problems during the research process. The respondents were given a waiver regarding the confidentiality of their identity and the information that they did not wish to disclose. The researcher eagerly sought the respondents' cooperation, and they were assured that the data gathered would be treated with the strictest confidence. These measures were taken with the hope of promoting trust between the researcher and the respondents.

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